

A Cultural Reflection of China's Tobacco Technology

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Abstract: *In the background of global tobacco control smoking, tobacco technology as a technology with a clear negative effect, has not disappeared from time to time in the world, but has gradually narrowed down the scale and social impact in the efforts of governments, Which in addition to economic, institutional, technical factors, but also contains a profound cultural roots. From the perspective of Social science and technology, taking the tobacco industry technology in China as an example, the tobacco culture has emphasized the traditional culture of Chinese culture, the spread of tobacco standards to traditional Chinese culture, the inheritance of tobacco to traditional hierarchical concepts. The cultural characteristics of smoking behavior in the field of social life, and the systematic analysis of the social function of the decision-making of China's tobacco technology development, the humanization of technological products and the huge technical premium, and the deep cultural connotation of the tobacco industry and the long-term impact of technology on social culture, from the perspective of social and cultural barriers to smoke control has a certain significance.*

Key words: *China's Tobacco, Tobacco Technology, Industrial Technology, Cultural Analysis, Cultural Reflection.*

1 Questions raised

With the rise of the world's anti-smoking campaign, people are increasingly concerned about health, forcing the tobacco industry through the use of advanced scientific and technological means to reduce cigarette tar for the purpose of reducing the harm to the human body, trying to get out of a smoking and health between the middle of the road , To meet consumer demand [1]. Global tobacco control work from the establishment of monitoring, monitoring and evaluation systems to monitor the use of tobacco; the implementation of smoking ban in public places to protect people from secondhand smoke; to provide help for smokers to quit; warning tobacco hazards; ban on tobacco advertising, promotion and sponsorship; Improve tobacco taxes and price six aspects of comprehensive development [2].

China as the world's largest tobacco producer and consumer, the government through a steady push of the ban on smoking and tobacco control policy is to plan to reduce the tobacco industry in the field of production and sales, by prohibiting tobacco advertising, smoking in public places and other forms of legislation to achieve tobacco The effective regulation of the industry, through the public's conscious resistance to tobacco consumption is shrinking, and achieved some success in the process of global tobacco control plays an important role. However, due to the long-term domestic dependence on tobacco products and large industries involved in many complex social relations, want to completely abolish the tobacco industry in the short term is not realistic. From the technical point of view, the development of China's tobacco industry is not only the epitome of the evolution of tobacco technology, but also with a strong traditional social and cultural mark. Therefore, for China's tobacco industry technology considerations, to integrate into the cultural factors, from the technical and cultural interaction between the start, look at the tobacco industry technology load the profound cultural connotation and technology on social and cultural long-term impact.

2 The rise of China's tobacco industry

Tobacco is a family of herbs, native to Central and South America. In 1492, Columbus discovered the new continent, that is, to see the local Indians smoke tobacco, showing that smoking practice before Columbus arrived in the Americas already exist, was originally a sacrifice function. Later the tobacco was introduced by the Spanish and Portuguese to Europe and Asia in the Philippines.

According to archaeological discoveries, tobacco in 1540 years ago by Southeast Asia, China's Guangdong near the coastal area of Vietnam, Guangdong is the earliest place of tobacco in China. China tobacco industry, including tobacco products, tobacco, cigarette paper, filter holding, tobacco tow and tobacco special machinery and other related production and sales enterprises and management departments, is set agriculture, industry, business in one of the large industrial groups, including tobacco Product production is the core of the tobacco industry.

Since the reform and opening up, China has been implementing a unified management of the tobacco monopoly system, January 1, 1982 China Tobacco Corporation has become the formal establishment of China's tobacco industry began. China National Tobacco Corporation is approved by the State Council set up a large state-owned enterprises, is a national agricultural trade and business integration, with legal personality of the economic entity. China's tobacco monopoly on the production, sale and import and export business monopoly of the organization system. Tobacco Monopoly Bureau at all levels and tobacco companies to take a set of institutions two brands of operation.

3 Technical System of China 's Tobacco Industry Technology

Professor Chen Changshu believes that industrial technology is reflected in the actual production process, the production process or service process technology, is the production object, production object, the service object is closely related to the technology, is the object of technology, technology is the basis of industrial technology, But not with the object of the process is not a reality of industrial technology. Industrial technology is composed of a variety of technology complex, is the system of technology [3]. Industrial technology is the evolution of technology to the industrial level of the form. American philosopher Karl Mitchell attributes the form of technology as a process to the invention, design, manufacture, and use. Professor Yuande Yu believes that the technical system of production technology is industrial technology. The technical invention that is produced by the technical conception and creativity is the initial form of the technology. It must be objectively and materialized by design, trial and experiment, and it can be incorporated into the process of production labor and become the production technology [4]. In accordance with this understanding, industrial technology must be a combination of a variety of production technologies, there must be a number of matching with a series of production technology and auxiliary technology in order to form products and services, and only complete the production technology system, in order to achieve Technical product purpose. The large technical system of tobacco industry technology just confirms these views.

According to the " China 's Tobacco Encyclopedia" [5] division, China's tobacco industry technology is divided into five general technical system and a new tobacco technology system. First, tobacco and tobacco technology system, involving tobacco baking and grading technology, breeding technology, nursery technology, pest control technology; Second, tobacco processing technology system, involving tobacco fermentation technology, cigarette formula technology, silk technology, cigarette coiling technology And tobacco and cigarette packaging technology; Third, tobacco storage and transportation technology system, involving cigarette products, dry and wet humidity control technology, cigarette storage and storage technology, cigarettes and other cigarettes and other products and cigarettes custody maintenance technology, tobacco storage pest control Technology, cigarette transport technology; fourth, tobacco enterprise management technology system, involves the tobacco enterprise management decision, the tobacco enterprise brand and the image, the tobacco enterprise plan management, the production management, the science and technology management, the tobacco enterprise equipment management, the material management, the quality management, the product development management, the tobacco Enterprise cost management, etc .; Fifth, tobacco purchase and quality testing technology system, involving the tobacco purchase requirements and management, residual measurement technology, quality inspection and testing technology, assessment technology, smoke assessment technology, tar determination technology. In addition, the tobacco new technology system mainly refers to the reduction of technology, automatic control technology, and hundreds of smoking cessation technology is also among the tobacco industry technology.

Tobacco technology involves agriculture, industry, commerce in all areas, each area and the use of strict technical standards. In China's tobacco industry, a huge technical system, each type of technology is also a small technical system. In the perspective of technical sociology, technology and culture is a kind of you have me, I have your interaction. Tobacco industry technology development process, the technical system through the social and cultural exchanges to change the form and appearance of social culture, frequent changes, improved and updated tobacco products, in general, to build a material by the tobacco product culture world. Tobacco industry technology from the instrument level performance through the smoke and brand culture to convey the national cultural information, the system culture layer reflects the China's Tobacco monopoly system of business, from the spiritual and cultural level of the performance of a positive attitude of social psychology.

4 China's tobacco industry technology culture embedded

4.1 The origin of religious culture of tobacco

Smoking is a cultural phenomenon, is the long-term form of life, and runs through the political and economic life. According to the literature, in ancient times, smoking was a prayer ritual for Mexican indigenous people. In the mythology of the Tartoska people, smoke is the only medium of contact between man and god, and the smoke is the food of the gods. Two thousand years ago the Maya people believe that the rain god Abu is a lot of smoking. Therefore, that smoke is the god of food, only the representatives of the gods can smoke. It can be seen that the production of tobacco is also a way of expressing the special hope for nature. In our country, smoking does not have the imprint of religious culture, but has a deep cultural mark. Smoking has a distinctive geographical characteristics, reflecting the unique characteristics of national culture, many ethnic minority areas popular chewing tobacco, and some places will be transferred into the water of tobacco, called smoke. Yunnan ethnic minorities have their own cigarette dancing, chimney dance, with utensils to do props have become a culture. Many places of traditional smoking from the traditional tradition of heritage, customs of the infection, rather than the individual's active choice.

4.2 Chinese traditional communication etiquette to achieve the promotion of tobacco

China is famous for its etiquette, so people attach great importance to rituals in their lives. Initially, the widespread spread of tobacco is both a demand for living and a need for social etiquette. Late Qing Dynasty was written, seven things to open the door, today eight carry on. Meaning that the rice wine salt and sugar tea smoke, smoke also included in the indispensable daily necessities of life [6]. Cigarettes have become a traditional etiquette in the smoke, toast, respect for a tea. Tobacco initially spread in China, the two main reasons, one of its emphasis on the prevention and treatment of disease prevention and treatment, with traditional Chinese medicine moxibustion and smoking therapy fusion. Second, China is known as the etiquette of the state, the traditional culture attaches great importance to interpersonal relationships, after the succession of tobacco, and soon become the same important tea and alcohol hospitality items [7]. With the modern modern tobacco evolving into a simple hobby different, China's tobacco consumption has always been with respect for performance and friendship - a strong traditional culture, by smoking, respect for smoke to express respect for others. Tobacco products, gifts and communication functions of China's tobacco consumption is also an important reason for the high.

4.3 The spread of Chinese traditional culture information

Cigarettes of the trademark, because the Chinese cigarettes have a strict class, two categories, three categories of distinction, coupled with the tobacco industry enterprises belong to the regional culture of different cigarettes reflect a more intense cultural color.

From the pattern point of view, there are several major design methods: First, the monuments, famous products, ancient artifacts designed for the title of the smoke standard. Such as Huangguoshu, the Great Hall of the people, three color, heavy nine, Yellow Crane Tower, wide and narrow, Shanhaiguan, Yueyang floor, Tiananmen Square, the front door, Grand View Garden. Second, the memorial to the historical time such as the International Labor Day to commemorate the "May Day", a symbol of the Chinese nation "China." Third, named after the local names, such as Changsha, Beijing, Lanzhou, Chongqing, Qingdao and so on. In the national culture, the dragon symbolizes auspicious, so only with the "dragon" word smoke standard there are more than 70 kinds, such as the Long Township, the dragon is not the same as the Chinese people, Dragon Po, Dragon Girl, a dragon pattern of the cigarette is more than 200 kinds [8].

Smoke is also a concrete manifestation of Chinese traditional culture preferences. As we all know, the Chinese people like red, red in China's traditional festivals and important celebrations are auspicious symbol of happiness. Therefore, the Chinese cigarette cigarette brand design into the "red" element is an important feature, there are red double happiness, the Red River and other well-known brands. Followed by the "gold" of the distinguished and "king" of the supreme status of the like, there are gold mango, hibiscus Wang and other cigarettes. Chinese cigarettes showcase the traditional Chinese culture to the world through the display of scenic spots, scenic spots, cultural relics, ancient and modern characters, valuable calligraphy and painting, arts and sports, national costumes, animal plants and so on. Such as "West Lake card" cigarettes is a West Lake ten King, "Mountain Resort" cigarettes show is Chengde Mountain Resort and other local attractions. In this sense, the smoke standard has become a medium for traditional cultural transmission and cultural exchange.

4.4 Tobacco is the appearance of grade and identity

In China, different brands of cigarettes brand differences on the choice of consumers a great impact on the same level of cigarette brand differentiation is very large, the difference between origin and pin on the impact of consumers is also great. Many times, the choice of what brand of cigarettes, not only people like the expression, more people are an important medium of communication, is the embodiment of the economic strength and social status of smokers, mainly due to China's special tobacco grading system. In China, more than 150 cigarette industry enterprises produced nearly 2200 cigarette grades (including specifications), the vast majority can only be sold in the province or the region, almost all domestic cigarettes are sold in the domestic market, the national brand is not More common. Unlike other countries, tobacco prices are not the same as the price of tobacco in China, there are clear classification of cigarettes, cigarettes have a clear class, two categories, three categories, different brands and the same brand of high school low-end product price differences are Very great. Tobacco consumption has the characteristics of diversification, individuality and art, and contains more and more complicated cultural information. The grade of smoke is still enough to show the level of identity, making the core function of smoke is completely replaced by features, especially the additional function, and become a consumer culture, luxury consumption pursuit, a kind of psychological expression. Need to promote healthy and healthy lifestyle from the social and cultural level, fundamentally curb people's tobacco consumption psychology.

4.5 Tobacco becomes a cultural act and a way of life

Cigarettes in the trademark art, formula technology, manufacturing process will reflect the country's living habits and ways of communication. Xu Zhimo has written "smoking and culture," a text that Oxford education success is the secret of its tutor system. The secret of the mentor, according to Professor Likak, said, "is aimed at their disciples smoking." It is very troublesome to find a nonsmoking student in Oxford or Cambridge - not to mention it. Learn to smoke, learn the quilt on the sofa sitting on the law, learn half-engraved talk - college education is enough [9].

Visible, smoking has developed into a gesture of the show. Sometimes smoking can determine the character of the people, minors smoking is also included in the ranks of adults, a reflection of psychological activity. Female smoking has become a symbol of the shackles of traditional forces. The cigarette brand is not a simple description of the product name, but a comprehensive concept that encompasses the specific core functions of the product, the explicit benefit guarantee, the value scale, the cultural connotation, the personalization, and the specific consumption level. This concept is the consumer market The product of development. Consumers often according to their own consumer needs to judge, choose, buy cigarettes products. Different brands, reflecting the consumer-specific quality evaluation criteria. The cigarette brand because of its both the basic properties of goods and cultural connotation of the characteristics, making the principle of consumption of smoke in the indispensable principles include the brand [10].

At the cognitive level, the brand is the name or symbol used to distinguish it from the competitor's product or service, but in the customer's mind it is not just a name, a simple sign, but a customer's Kind of emotional, ideal or memories of a spiritual level of things [11]. The brand sustenance of the consumer's emotional and spiritual experience, in the minds of consumers to form a specific personality characteristics, so that consumers have some kind of satisfaction, experience, memories or ideals. Therefore, the need for smoking and tobacco control in the process of brand consolidation through the way to eliminate this emotional dependence and psychological sustenance.

5 Conclusion

Through the above analysis shows that China's tobacco industry technology is different from other tobacco industry technology unique cultural characteristics. This cultural character contains the emphasis on culture at the beginning of the tobacco, the transmission of tobacco to the traditional Chinese ritual culture, the spread of the cigarette on the traditional Chinese culture, the inheritance of tobacco to the traditional hierarchical concept and the appearance of smoking in the social life field. This kind of cultural characteristics through the people's consumption behavior and consumption habits in the development of China's tobacco industry, and become the decision of China's tobacco technology development direction of the important factors, bringing technical products, man-made level and huge technical premium.

Therefore, in the process of smoking and tobacco control, cannot simply from the tobacco industry to carry out containment and regulation, but also from the social and cultural start, by curbing consumerism culture, advocate healthy lifestyle lifestyle, eliminate smoking behavior for people's emotional dependence

and Social and psychological impact, for the global ban on tobacco smoking has a certain significance.

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